

1 **Gpr31 and Gpr146 distinguish cDC1 and cDC2.**

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6 We measured total transcription in dendritic cell subsets: the cDC type 1 or cDC1, and in the cDC2. We
7 report here discovery of G-protein coupled receptors (Gpr) that fully distinguished BDCA1+ and BDCA3+
8 DC populations. CDC1 specifically expressed CD31, while cDC2 specifically expressed CD146. These
9 Gpr family receptors are suitable for isolation and study of the dendritic cell types.

10 Citations

11 1. Schlitzer, A., Sivakamasundari, V., Chen, J., Sumatoh, H.R.B., Schreuder, J., Lum, J., Malleret, B.,
12 Zhang, S., Larbi, A., Zolezzi, F. and Renia, L., 2015. Identification of cDC1-and cDC2-committed DC
13 progenitors reveals early lineage priming at the common DC progenitor stage in the bone marrow. *Nature*
14 *immunology*, 16(7), pp.718-728.

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